

ACCOUNTING OF INCOME OF DRUGS IN STATE MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS.

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Abstract: This article describes the legal basis and practical aspects of taking into account the input of drugs in state medical institutions. the issues of accounting for tools used in medicine are shown.

Keywords: State medical institution, accounting, cost, memorial order, documentation, budget classification.

it is important for the stable operation of the state medical institutions and for the patients to receive quality medical treatment on time, the provision of the institution with medicines and tools used in medicine.

we consider it expedient to touch upon the practical aspects of accounting for medicines and medical devices in the state medical institutions operating today.

One of the special features of accounting in state medical institutions is the organization of accounts and the formation of reports based on budget classification. also, reporting of the purchase, cash and real costs of medicines and medical equipment in state medical institutions is based on the "Instructions on the Application of Budget Classification".

in accordance with this instruction, the expenditure item 42 52 400 "Drugs, medical devices, vaccines and bacteriological preparations" includes drugs, medical devices (item 42 52 410) and vaccines and bacteriological preparations (item 42 52 420) purchase costs are reflected [2]. 42-52-410-drugs, 42-52-411-medical supplies, starting from January 1, 2021, in order to improve the process of identifying and analyzing the needs for medicines and medical devices from the funds allocated to healthcare organizations 42-52-412-reagents and reagents for medical equipment and supplies, 42-52-413-disinfectants and personal protective equipment, relevant changes and additions were made to the information system of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan [6].

accounting of medicines and medical devices in state medical institutions is also conducted in accordance with the current "Instructions on Accounting in Budget Organizations".

according to this instruction, medicines, components, bacterial preparations, serums in hospitals, treatment-prophylaxis, treatment-veterinary and cost estimates for these purposes are provided for in the sub-account 062 "Medicines and wound dressings" vaccines, blood and wound dressings and other medicines are taken into account [3]. it is appropriate to emphasize

another issue, that in order to harmonize budget accounting with international standards of financial reporting in the public sector, the standard of budget accounting of the Republic of Uzbekistan (BHS No. 2) "Uniform Chart of Accounts" was adopted.

161200 of this standard "Drugs, medical devices, vaccines and bacteriological preparations" in the appropriate sub-accounts of the hospital, treatment-prophylaxis, treatment-veterinary and cost estimates for these purposes are provided for medicines in organizations, tools used in medicine, components, vaccines, bacteriological preparations, sera, vaccines, blood and wound dressings, medicines given free of charge on the basis of a prescription to a contingent of privileged patients treated in outpatient settings drugs, medical supplies and other drugs of social importance are taken into account [4].

.in the sub-account in both of the above-mentioned documents, it is indicated that auxiliary and pharmacy materials in medical organizations that have their own pharmacies are also taken into account.

The receipt of medicines and medical devices is reflected separately in accounting and is received by the institution as a result of:

- purchase under a supply (sale) contract;

- involuntary descent (under a gift contract);

- issuing in a centralized manner (based on the distribution of higher organizations);

- determination of excess (unaccounted for) drugs and medical devices as a result of the inventory.

the purchase of medicines and medical equipment in state medical institutions with budgetary and extra-budgetary funds also requires separate analytical accounting in accounting.

drugs and medical devices are included in the accounting balance of the institution at cost, that is, they include the purchase price (amounts paid to the supplier) and all expenses related to their purchase.

when determining the costs associated with the purchase of medicines and medical supplies:

- their purchase price;

- customs duties and other taxes;

- transport-preparation costs and other costs directly related to their purchase are taken into account.

- excluding trade discounts, refunds and other similar circumstances [5]. Today, in state medical institutions, there are cases where the above-

mentioned costs are not included in the cost of the drugs and medical devices used in the accounting balance sheet of the institution.

Accounting transactions related to the receipt of drugs and medical devices are reflected as follows:

№	Content of transactions	DT	Ct	Supporting documents	memorial varrant
Purchase under a supply (sale) contract					
1	Drugs and medical equipment purchased from budget funds to the cost (purchase price, delivery and other additional costs)	091/1	150/1	invoice, document	6
2	To the cost of medicines and medical equipment purchased from extra-budgetary funds (purchase price, delivery and other additional costs)	091/3	150/3	invoice, document	6
3	Delivery of drugs and medical equipment purchased from budget funds at their actual value.	062/1	091/1	Accounting reference	6
4	Delivery of medicines and medical equipment purchased from extra-budgetary funds according to their value	062/3	091/3	Accounting reference	6
involuntary descent (under a gift contract)					
1	the value of drugs and medical devices taken arbitrarily from individuals (market value determined in the prescribed manner)	062/3	262	application, document	20

2	the value of drugs and medical devices taken arbitrarily from legal entities (market value determined in the prescribed manner, delivery, etc	091/3	150/3	invoice, document	20
3	Importation of drugs and medical devices obtained from legal entities according to their value.	062/3	091/3	accounting reference	20

Issuing in a centralized manner (based on the distribution of higher organizations).

1	importation of drugs and medical devices obtained in a centralized order (delivery and other additional costs according to the established order)	091/2	180/1	Accounting reference	20
2	importation of drugs and medical devices obtained in a centralized manner according to the actual value	062/2	091/2	Accounting reference	20
3	receiving from special funds centrally received medicines and medical devices according to their value (delivery and other additional costs according to the established procedure)	091/4	180/2	Accounting reference	20
4	import of drugs and medical equipment received from special funds in a centralized manner at their actual cost.	062/4	091/4	Accounting reference	20

Determination of excess (unaccounted for) inventories

1	Excess as a result of	062/1	273/1	Inventory	20
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	inventory import of drugs and medical devices.			record	
2	Excess as a result of inventory import of drugs and medical devices.	062/3	273/2	Inventory record	20A

In state medical institutions, the accounting of the receipt of medicines and medical devices is kept in separate analytical accounts according to the sources of their purchase.

in accounting, it is required to strictly follow the sequence of documenting the entry of drugs and medical devices.

Determining and documenting the costs associated with the purchase of drugs and medical devices at the actual value (cost) of the state medical institutions, that is, the contract for the type, series and unit of measurement of each drug and differences in invoices also lead to incorrect calculations. In addition, when importing medicines and medical devices, their expiration date is also important, and sometimes mistakes are made in these processes as well.

We believe that it is appropriate to pay special attention to the following when taking into account the income of medicines and medical devices in medical institutions operating in our country and financed from the state budget:

- when adding purchased medicines and medical devices to the balance sheet of the institution at cost, the expenses related to the purchase are added;
- strict adherence to the documentation sequence when accounting for the input of drugs and medical devices. This situation has a negative impact on the institution's financial statements;
- strict adherence to the expiration date of purchased medicines and medical devices;
- taking into account the income of the purchased medicines and medical devices according to the relevant cost classification (code).

List of used literature:

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2. number.

3. 2.Instruction "On the application of budget classification". It was registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 11, 2010 with number 2146.
4. 3.The Instruction "On accounting in budget organizations" was registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 22, 2010 with number 2169.
5. 4.The standard of budget accounting of the Republic of Uzbekistan (BHS No. 2) "Uniform Chart of Accounts". was registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 20, 2018 with number 3078.
6. 5.The standard of budget accounting of the Republic of Uzbekistan (BHS No. 7) "Inventories". registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 14, 2019 with number 3120.
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